

Search for New Oral Hypoglycemic Agents. Part III

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Several phenyl-substituted bis- $\alpha\alpha'$ -(*N*-phenyl, *N*-carbamyl, or thiocarbamyl) diaminoacetones and 1,4-(*N*-phenyl, *N*-carbamyl, or thiocarbamyl)phenylenediamines have been prepared for testing their hypoglycemic activity.

The accidental discovery of hypoglycemic action of carbutamide¹ and tolbutamide² set in a worldwide research for a substitute of insulin which may be effective when administered orally.

Keeping in view the observations of the previous workers³⁻¹⁴ in the field, we have prepared several bis- $\alpha\alpha'$ -(*N*-aryl, *N*-carbamyl, or thiocarbamyl) diaminoacetones (I: R=Cl, Me, OMe, H) and bis-1,4-(*N*-aryl, *N*-carbamyl, or thiocarbamyl)phenylenediamines (II: R=Cl, Me, OMe, H) in the present communication.

or

or

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In the present synthesis, *para*-substituted monophenylureas and -thiureas were prepared and were condensed with $\alpha\alpha'$ -dichloroacetone and 1,4-dibromobenzene separately.

The m.p., yields and analyses etc. of the compounds represented by (I) and (II) are reported in Tables I and II.

EXPERIMENTAL

Monophenyl (substituted) Ureas and Thiureas

A mixture of the hydrochloride (0.5M) of aniline, *p*-toluidine, *p*-chloroaniline, or *p*-anisidine and urea (0.5M) was refluxed in water (100ml); HCl (conc., 1 ml) and glacial acetic acid (5 ml) were then added. The corresponding crystalline mono-substituted phenylurea separated after 4 hours. These were filtered, dried, and recrystallised from absolute ethanol.

The mono-substituted phenylthiureas were prepared similarly from the corresponding amine hydrochloride and thiourea.

Dis- $\alpha\alpha'$ -(N-substituted phenyl-N-carbamyl) diaminoacetone.—A mixture of dichloroacetone (0.05M), phenylurea, tolylurea, *p*-chlorophenylurea, or *p*-anisylurea (0.25M each) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.25M) in absolute ethanol (15ml) was refluxed on a water bath for 12 to 14 hours in anhydrous condition. The substituted diaminoacetones were extracted with hot ethanol and recrystallised from the same solvent.

TABLE I

S.No.	R(4')	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
$\text{H}_2\text{N.CO.N.} \left(\begin{array}{c} \diagup \quad \diagdown \\ \text{---} \quad \text{---} \\ \diagdown \quad \diagup \\ \text{X}_R \end{array} \right) . \text{CH}_2 . \text{CO} . \text{CH}_2 . \text{N.} \left(\begin{array}{c} \diagup \quad \diagdown \\ \text{---} \quad \text{---} \\ \diagdown \quad \diagup \\ \text{X}_R \end{array} \right) . \text{CO} . \text{NH}_2$						
1	Cl	213°	68%	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₂	14.10	14.21
2	H	208°	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₄	16.90	17.20
3	Me	182°	70	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₄	15.60	15.81
4	OMe	190°	62	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₄	14.91	14.94
$\text{H}_2\text{N.CS.N.} \left(\begin{array}{c} \diagup \quad \diagdown \\ \text{---} \quad \text{---} \\ \diagdown \quad \diagup \\ \text{X}_R \end{array} \right) . \text{CH}_2 . \text{CO} . \text{CH}_2 . \text{N.} \left(\begin{array}{c} \diagup \quad \diagdown \\ \text{---} \quad \text{---} \\ \diagdown \quad \diagup \\ \text{X}_R \end{array} \right) . \text{CS} . \text{NH}_2$						
5	Cl	254°	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ON ₄ Cl ₂ S ₂	13.00	13.14
6	H	215°	74	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ ON ₄ S ₂	15.57	15.64
7	Me	225°	70	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ ON ₄ S ₂	14.48	14.50
8	OMe	234°	65	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₄ S ₂	13.10	13.40

Bis- $\alpha\alpha'$ -(N-substituted phenyl-N-thiocarbamyl) diaminoacetone.—Dichloroacetone (0.05M) was refluxed with mono-substituted phenylthiureas (0.25M) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.25M) in absolute ethanol for 12 to 14 hours. The resulting diaminoacetone derivatives were isolated as described above.

1,4-(*N*-Substituted phenyl-*N*-carbonyl)phenylenediamine.—A mixture of *p*-dibromobenzene (0.05*M*), monoaryl urea (0.25*M*) (phenyl-, tolyl-, *p*-chlorophenyl- or *p*-anisyl-urea) in ethanol (10 ml) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.25*M*) was refluxed in anhydrous condition on a water bath for 22 to 24 hours. It was filtered hot. The filtrate on cooling afforded a crystalline compound which was recrystallised from hot absolute ethanol

TABLE II

S.No.	R(4').	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
$\text{H}_2\text{N.CO.N.} \left(\langle \langle \text{---} \rangle \times \text{R} \rangle \right) \langle \langle \text{---} \rangle \rangle \text{N.} \left(\langle \langle \text{---} \rangle \times \text{R} \rangle \right) .\text{CO.NH}_2$						
1	H	94°	52%	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄	16.98	16.20
2	Cl	81°	56	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₂	13.47	13.52
3	Me	112°	52	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₄	14.91	14.97
4	OMe	96°	54	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₄	13.50	13.80
$\text{H}_2\text{N.CS.N.} \left(\langle \langle \text{---} \rangle \times \text{R} \rangle \right) \langle \langle \text{---} \rangle \rangle \text{N.} \left(\langle \langle \text{---} \rangle \times \text{R} \rangle \right) .\text{CS.NH}_2$						
5	H	92°	60	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ S ₂	14.56	14.80
6	Cl	86°	64	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ Cl ₂ S ₂	12.38	12.56
7	Me	98°	60	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₄ S ₂	13.56	13.80
8	OMe	84°	62	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₄ S ₂	12.62	12.80

1,4-(*N*-Substituted phenyl-*N*-thiocarbonyl)phenylenediamines were prepared as above. In this case mono-substituted phenylthioureas were taken in place of mono-substituted phenylureas.

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